

Pāgali: An Ethno-Psychological Analysis in Bengali Culture.

Md. Insan Ali

Ph.D. Research Scholar
Department of History
Jadavpur University. Kolkata

Abstract

Senseless, Eccentric, Idiotic, Lunatic, Mental illness, and Abnormal Behaviour, in simple Bengali language whom we call in ‘Pāgali’ (Mad Women) Age after age, how they are discussed or criticized in history. Maybe they have peculiarly been discussed through ages or whose talk or silence is improper, meaningless, unreasonable, or laughable to the civilized society or whose behaviour is not natural but the outward expression of mental derangement in the aspect of the civilized society. They have been considered to be unwanted by the civilized people time and again from the distant past to the present times. But why? It is because they are called ‘Pāgali’ in civil society. However, by using the Bengali word ‘Pāgali’ (Female Insane) very much in vogue in Bengali society. Society has taught us to identify by this word man from whom it is well and good to keep distance because he is mad to the extreme and unwanted. So whatever they may appear to the eye insane, devoid of common sense, nonsense, or mentally obsessed, it is certainly necessary to throw light on their lives in the study of social history on the basis of the word ‘Pāgali’.

Keywords: *Pāgali, Mad Women, Female Insane, Idiotic, Lunatic, Mental illness, Abnormal Behaviour.*

Introduction :

The expressions devoid of common-sense, mentally deranged, idiocy, and insane are all synonymous with the simple Bengali word is ‘Pāgali’ (Mad Women). We all know how the civilized people form the idea about the manners, self-mood, and gestures of those who have been getting queerly discussed and criticized for ages or whose conversation or silence is unjust, meaningless, unreasonable, or laughable to the polished society and whose outward conduct is not normal or exposes mental derangement in the opinion of the civilized world or in whose minds the society and civilization have created a ‘different kind of condition’ or whose natural tendency, to the society, its irrational, devoid of common-sense of nonsensical.¹ Some find them to be psychiatric patients and some find them mad.² The Women man is not willing to listen to their illogical conversation or understand their silent manners for the reason

that they are comparatively rather modest as well as frantic.³ Their right place is a lunatic asylum or a psychiatrist's chamber. They have been getting unwanted by the civilized people frequently from the middle age to the present times. But why? Has the civilized world been thus criticizing them through the ages? Why is anything about them presented perversely? The cause is that they are '*Pāgali*' to the civilized society. However, by the use of the word '*Pāgali*' in our discussible research-work-the word which is in use in the society and culture of Bengal it is evident that by this word the society and civilization have taught us to identify a man from whom it is safe to keep distance, for, he is crazy to the extreme and unwanted⁴. whatever may be remarked by the civilized world, such as unwanted, illogical, insane, devoid of common sense, nonsense, indifferent, mentally obsessed, etc. So let us discuss the fundamentally provable subject on the basis of the word '*Pāgali*'.

Research Question :

Who is Pāgali? Who are the Pāgali? Why are they Pāgali? Whom does the society call Pāgali and in what interest? What is the outlook of the society and civilization regarding the Pāgali? How many relations of mental disease are there with it? What is the result of scientific or medical studies in this regard? And how much correct in the explanation they give? Primarily it is not the main matter in the discussible research-work to present the history of the Pāgali. The basic purpose is to show the society's harmony with how they are discussed in society, how the motion in the name of Pāgali has been existing in the culture of the Bengalee from the ancient time especially in the sin the social life of Bengal and how has it gradually appeared in our culture in different forms. Another purpose is to highlight how this motion through the diverse conduct of the Pāgali has mingled with the social life, that is, society, culture, religions, and political life. As very little is discussed as regards the outcast in all the civilizations of the world, very little has been discussed from the historical point of view about the Pāgali (the fatuous person) who forms a special section of the outcast. But what is the function of history? It may be said very naturally that if the function of history becomes the study of humanism it is certainly necessary to discuss those absent-minded pavement-dwellers with matted locks of hair, who are called Pāgali unhesitatingly⁵. If this running stage of the story of progress shows consistency in the human society and Civilization becomes history, why should not the fatuous persons be discussed in the history of the progress of human society? In another relevance, the meaning of the word '*Pāgali*' is diversely in use in the life and conception of the Bengalee.⁶ In our society this Pāgali has become sometimes frantic, sometimes mentally deranged, and

again sometimes frenzied, sometimes idiotic, crazy, maniac, off the head, psychiatric patient, lunatic, curious- these are all the manifestations of the Pāgali in one after another majestic form. There is still another exposure to the neurotic *Pāgali* in cultural life⁷. All taken together, the meaning of the word '*Pāgali*' has become manifold.

Objectivity:

To make an attempt to analyse the socio-economic condition of the Mad Women with an eye to materialist philosophy; in this case, however, to present the realistic history of the Mad Women from the historical point of view in the oriental thought rejecting Foucauldian thought; especially centring on the pluralistic concept of the Mad Women and the Mad Women like behaviour in Bengal's culture, to endeavour to explain the social, cultural and clinical outlook. To make an earnest effort how to throw light on the history of the Mad Women-like behaviour in the Indian perspective detaching it from the western cultivation of knowledge. Specially to produce in the social life of Bengal, a sociological interpretation of the idea of the plurality of the Mad Women group.

The Idea of Pāgali in Bengali Culture:

As soon as we hear the word *Pāgali* diverse images flash before our eyes.⁸ Generally mad women are known as *Pāgali* in our society. Many stories are involved with the life of this *Pāgali*. The girl child who was affectionately brought up on the lap of her parents, spends her days today perhaps on the footpath like vagrants or in a place close to a railway station. Everyday own eyes catch the sight of such more or fewer *pāgli*'s. The stories of their lives have been lighted very little. But they also are human beings. Why is their condition like this? Why have they chosen the *Pāgali*'s life leaving their family and relations? Does she whom we call *Pāgali* know if she is actually a *Pāgali*? How does society look upon them? The arising of such curiosity in the mind of man is natural. The women who are psychotic patients suffering from mental disorders and are mentally deranged etc. leave their place breaking the social land at a certain time after tolerating the society's insult and deprivation. Then she begins her new life, wandering in the streets and asking for something laying her hand because of organic demand and also satisfying her hunger by eating the residue of food left. Gradually then the woman is known as a *Pāgali*. The page has been interpreted from different points of view in sociology. She has been reared with affection and has stayed on the footpath in a time before the hateful eyes. When a father addresses her daughter caressingly- "*Oh My little Pāgli*

” or when a lover says to his lady-love, ”*Ore Amar Pāgali re....*” In such use of the sentences, the *Pāgali* sometimes becomes full of affection and sometimes again an object of love. But those *Pāgali* s who are truly mental patients and expelled from the society lead a very difficult life , they struggle for existence at every moment. Many perhaps hold fate or destiny responsible for the pitiable condition of the *Pāgali*’s . But if is not the main subject to discuss whether this fate or destiny is responsible or not. As a matter of fact, it is the main objective to conjure up a picture of the society of real life. Where is the actual relation of the society with the *Pāgali* who is sitting on the roadside being driven out of society? A nice example may be set to make it clear that the *Pāgali*’s also have love in their minds and they cherish wishes and desires even in their minds. But why she is a *Pāgali* in our main mystery We can try to understand this by mentioning the context of “*Pāgali* ”, book of short stories edited by Santi Dhar (‘*Pāgali*’- 1976) . Shampa Dutta, a girl of the class of v, see every day on the way back from school a *Pāgali* sitting in the raised terrace outside their house also most every day the *Pāgali* beckons her with a call saying, “ come along to see my daughter her look here, my daughter is lying asleep; just come on for once only, please.” She makes *Shampa* understand this by beckoning to her, *Shapma* comes step by step to her. In the meantime, the *Pāgali* has taken out a big doll from her small bundle. Look, here is my daughter, my daughter’s frack has been torn, will you give a frock? *Shampa* said that she would. Just after this moment, *Shampa* said, “Why are you sitting here?” Have you no home?” The *Pāgali* at once, muttering ‘oh oh’, went her unknown way putting the girl-doll in the bundle. *Shampa* kept looking in that direction. Thus went on the conversation between *Shampa* and the *Pāgali* . But all of a sudden *Shampa* came to know that the *Pāgali* just died. At once *Shampa* ran and seeing the *Pāgali* , bust into cries. But why did *Shampa* cry out? In fact, love and affection act as the uniting bond between mind and soul. When we are bound by the bond of attachment, the feeling of coming out of it or leaving the things of that attachment behind while departing from the world is differently expressed and it is too deep for words ⁹.

The famous poem ‘*Pāgali* ’ of Kumares Ghosh (*Unmada* , 1987) in this connection may be mentioned. If the subject matter of the poem is discussed, the life of the *Pāgali* becomes clearly familiar to us. The girl sits on the curb of the pavement. She is dressed in torn, dirty clothes and has a torn chemise on. She has dry, unoiled, disheveled hair. Her body is soiled with dust. Lifting her eyes to the sky the girl is laughing and also is lowering down her eyes and in the next moment, she is looking at the same laughter. She has no reason to laugh but still is

laughing. She goes on muttering unreasonable utterances, sometimes to herself. I came to know her as a *Pāgali*. God touched lightly with a paint-brush her beauty all over her body, no doubt; but he did not have the brush well-washed before use, nor did he pour two spoonfuls of sense and brains into her head. Perhaps he did not find out his container of brains near at hand and as such, it happened to be a misdeed. But there is no sorrow in the mind of the *Pāgali* for this, nor is any grievance or complaint. Rather She has much curiosity in her eyes and face. So, looking again and again at the sky, she, as if, is saying o God! What a leader of the good-for-nothing you are! The specimen of the truth of this is that I am sitting here on this pavement before the people and you are laying hidden behind the cloud in fear of public scandal, aren't you?¹⁰

Light has been thrown differently on the *Pāgali* in different areas of literature. In various literary works of Rabindranath, *Pāgali* has been seen in different perspectives, viz, such as in *Bani* poem, chara's picture in '*Yoginda*' from rhyme-picture, in the drama of '*Chandalika*', in the story '*Samapti*', in the essay of '*Jivan-Smriti*' and in the drama '*Raktakaravi*' and in the stories '*Subha-dristi*' and '*Baistami*' the *Pāgali* has become a folktales' full of diverse significances. Again, Rabindranath has seen this *Pāgali* as a mad woman. In the book of poems, '*Sanartari*', '*Puravi*', '*Kalpna-Varsasesh*', in the essay entitled '*Raja-Praja*', in the story '*Pragati-sanghar*', in the dramas '*Bhangna-Hridaya*' and '*Tapati*' and in the essay '*Bihari-laal*' he has given a set of different shades to the *Pāgali* in different meanings¹¹. It may be concluded that one of the examples of the *Pāgali* sequences that are expressed in the Bengali literatures culture and thought is traced in the lives of women. This *Pāgali* in terms of fondness and elation, affection and compose and sometimes in love has become by conception a many-sided entity.

Mad Women and Society:

The *Pāgali*'s are carefree till there occurs no direct clash with the society. The society does not know the exact moment form when a man begins to be a *Pāgali*. As long as the society is ignorant of this, the *Pāgali* has no problem. For he can go on thinking without any obstacle. He can move delightfully in the circle of consciousness where there appears the vicious circle in its own course of rule. The circumference moving round the circle of thought ends at that point which was its starting dot. Then in a certain moment someone senses it. Perhaps noticing his speaking to himself someone is surprised or feels it to be full of curiosity. The existence

of another Pāgali comes to notice. The Pāgali's struggle begins. It is the life-termination struggle of going against the rules of this society. In this struggle the society does not come to help him. Some members of society with whom the neo-Pāgali has no relation of spirit, stay with for a few days. When this number of the members getting smaller and smaller is reduced to nil and if the Pāgali lives up to that time, the real life of the Pāgali begins¹².

The psychologists think that every person is abnormal; of course, he is considered to be normal up to a certain limit. If one sits down opening the dictionary of abnormal psychology, one will notice the names and descriptions of many diseases¹³. It seems that if every individual is properly judges, almost all the people will be brought within the reach of some disease or other. He who became the Mad Women, remained separated from the others in his own thinking line, but what happens to him who stays released with him in society? What message does the Mad Women's behavior send every day to those who are the Mad Women's father, mother or brother and sister? Even if all people turn their faces from the Mad Women, the house he belongs to end the members of that house cannot ignore the abnormal life of one of their family¹⁴. If anyone goes mad, there is a mental consolation; but what do the household men of that person do when he remains normal in all other affairs except that special one at the mention of which he bursts into anger and utters obscene words of abuse¹⁵. In this context here the logic giving philosophers are particularly worthy mention. The logic-giving philosophers said of the 'rootless direct'. Each direct thing has a root or reality. There is no root or reality, but someone perceives something directly-this is the characteristic of 'rootless direct'. In the lifetime man falls a prey to many kinds of baseless thoughts. In such circumstances there is no certainly that all people, obeying the advice of the physician or utilizing their own discretion, will be able to come out of the world of those baseless thoughts. The main cause of this is that human mind is very surprising and mysterious. No rule of controlling the mind has yet been evolved. It is because every individual in the world is different and every mind is different. To know what a person cherishes in his mind is almost impossible. So even being the mother, she is late in guessing the mental deviation of her son or daughter. Again, a would-be Mad Women may continue to play act with the very nearest man. All taken together, it is a complicated chemistry. What can be realized in midst of this complication, is that a so-called sound mind cannot understand a so-called ailing mind and vice versa. He who will become the Mad Women in midst of these close relations, will stay self-absorbed by creating a circular region around him through his separation, but we can

guess the feelings of those who will be pained to think him to be the Mad Women. But it is a strange situation. A Mad Women and his sound kinsmen are inhabitants of two such worlds of which one is normal and another is abnormal¹⁶. This demarcation-line of normal-abnormal is determined by man. But does nature want any Mad Women? Many such people are found in the society, who by keeping pace with his surroundings, behave mental balance, they behave like the Mad Women in a particular sphere of life on account of some disparity.

Diversities of the Mad Women:

Do the Mad Women follow one another? They should not do so. For every Mad Women is of different nature. In fact there are endless diversities among the Mad Women. This arrangement of diversities exists also in human beings. But as man, having lost these under different pressures of civilization, behave like on shaped in a mould of puppet, that, diversity is not so noticeable¹⁷. In comparison the Mad Women have not that problem and as such, they are very much spontaneous from the standpoint of behaviour. The reference to those who have lost mental balance because of tyranny, repression, exploitation etc is different. For example, in the case of person like of Nabarun Bhattacharya's novel '*Zuddha Paristhiti*', the psychologists have certain clues in their hands. But this advantage is not available in the cases of those who, living their healthy lives, suddenly begin one day to enter into their self-made circle¹⁸. Among these types of the Mad Women there remains a lot of diverse surprising examples. Suppose, you have seen so many diverse forms and figures of Mad Women like behaviour in your experience. It is not that those are all sorrowful. Some figures have surprised you; some have left you puzzled as well. Again, some have passed by giving you genuine humour. Even retaining, themselves in many of them go on behaving like the Mad Women's in various ways¹⁹. Some of them are probably familiar to you²⁰. Perhaps we sometimes accept their sudden bursts of behaviour like the Mad Women in our everyday experience of such seeing. Perhaps you can realize that he manages²¹ to make his protest somewhere²¹. Even a hundred years ago there was no necessary time for thinking of the Mad Women in the minds of the common public. Our society has not regarded the Mad Women as a human being for a long time. So, tolerating the social negligence and tyranny for age after age the Mad Women's left the world with silent sensitiveness. Today being faced with this time we do not think that the common man's notion about the Mad Women has changed much better. As the romantic Mad Women like *Pagalini Radha* written by *Atin Bandopadhaya*²² or the character of '*Pagalini Kotha*' as drawn by Somdatta Bhattacharya had their place on the pages of literature, have got

over the difficulty. If they had lived in reality, They would have been hardcore Mad Women. In comparison the semblance of Sirshendu's Mad Women characters, though slight, is found in semi-towns or villages. Is there any security of the Mad Women or any independent leading of life? Will it be right to evaluate the Mad Women from all sides by only seeing them confined in the lunatic asylum like convicts? No, never. Analysing the data collected from the ways of their lives in the asylum, we can probably feel a little about the Mad Women. But it is impossible to analyse by this data the standard measurement of the Mad Women like behaviour and the mystery of the lifestyle of those who are vagabonds and whose place to pass the nights is footpath²³.

Conclusion:

Have we yet succeeded in understanding the demands of the Mad Women, especially the condition of his mind would? The man who is mentally abnormal does not actually want to trust the surrounding circumstance we can guess the causes of that mistrust, but can we say anything for certain? What is he thinking in fact or what does he want to do? In the case of a sound man as well, exactly the same words can be said. As a matter of fact, this failure in pursuit of the workings of the human mind is the main problem of psychology. There is long history also discussed for the past roll of time²⁴. We draw lessons from history. Similarly, psychology has been researching for ages in connection with the Mad Women and Mad Women-like behaviour, and the history of that research on the Mad Women deals with where its bond of unity with the society lies. As it is a main problem of psychology to realize the human mind, so it is the same problem of society as well. That is why the parents fail to understand their children. A friend fails to understand his friend. In the sphere of love also the extent of the lack of understanding is great. If it is seen from a little analytical viewpoint, it will be realized that this very failure to understand the minds of others gives impetus to the actions of becoming the Mad Women in society²⁵. Any Mad Women is more or less separated from society. He whose Mad Women-like behaviour, fortunately, has come to a halt before his absolute state of distress, cannot also unfold himself in all strata of society. The honest advice for sharing mental thoughts is being given all around night and day, but we more or less know how much difficult it is to get the environment and opportunity apt to share our intimate thoughts. The problem which you have overcome by will-force and how you have done it may not be suitable to remove another one's problem. Under these circumstances when a set of rules is framed in order to remove a definite mental problem, it naturally does not become all-reaching. In simple words, there is no fundamental rule for curing the Mad Women-like illness. There is no overall rule as well.

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